

LEARNING THEORIES APPLIED IN PRACTICE IN THE CLASSROOM

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Abstract

Learning Theories are of great importance in the teaching-learning process. The objective of this work is to understand the importance of such theories in the educational field. Different forms of learning were investigated as a series of stages and participants, including the teacher. It was concluded that learning theories enable the planning and elaboration of classes according to the thinkers of each theory.

Keywords: Theories. Learning. Living room. Class.

Introduction

The theme to be addressed by this article will be how the learning theories discussed in Educational Psychology are used in the classroom. Learning theories can be considered a basis for building knowledge of the different contents covered by subjects of all teaching modalities.

Boruchovitch (1999, p.11) explains that teachers working in Education have “little knowledge not only about how human intelligence is expressed, but also about the role of learning strategies, self-reflection and metacognitive processes in learning”.

It is presented in this context, the need for the teacher to keep up-to-date in the face of constant changes in the educational scenario, make use of technologies or their classes, and use learning theories as a way to diagnose and understand how each student learns in relation to the content covered. . This strategy can be seen as a solution to the difficulties and failures in the academic performance of certain students.

The Importance of Learning Theories in the Educational Scope

Educators are aware of the importance of learning theories, but they do not use them or do not yet know how to use this resource. Such educators know that the success or failure of a given student in relation to the content being worked on may be related to learning theories or

linked to environmental and psychological factors. Boruchovitch reports when talking about school failure, that:

[...] the possible causes of school failure, educators point out as main factors certain characteristics of the student, such as: low IQ, malnutrition, immaturity, emotional problems, parental abandonment, lack of economic conditions, disorganization family, among others. However, some researchers emphasize that there is no evidence that physical, biological and psychological problems are responsible for failures in the first grades, thus dispelling the myths of physical deficiencies, the disintegration of homes, intellectual retardation and lack of readiness. (BORUCHOVITCH, 1999, p. 7).

The problems faced by the teachers mentioned above are broadly related to one of the objects of study in Educational Psychology: learning theories. These theories explain the different situations according to your thinker or school representative.

Learning theories serve as an instrument to diagnose and analyze the different forms of learning, serving as a basis for the teacher to teach their classes with better quality and greater success. Each theory has its particularity, which is determined by its school or representative.

Learning in this way is seen as an interconnection of cognition, which in turn, presents an interrelationship with the development of knowledge and knowledge. The awareness of the real learning and development of the student in class is the result of different learning strategies concerning theories.

The concepts related to learning come from Psychology, and are based on the idea that the individual presents knowledge from experience. Thus, according to Neves and Damiani (2006), the new experiences acquired by popular and scientific knowledge are improved when new knowledge is incorporated. In this way, knowledge is seen as a chain of ideas that are added throughout daily experiences and practices.

A very relevant strategy is to make the student can self-assess, as in readings and group activities. The current pedagogical scenario demands that banking education be replaced, seen as the one in which the transmission of knowledge is carried out by the teacher, a figure who holds the knowledge and the truth and passes it on to the student. This change must be for more dynamic and interactive education, with a collective and collaborative teaching model, with the participation of all students and the teacher.

Therefore, learning theories are important not only for the success of the student's academic life, but also influence their education as a citizen and professional. With this, the teacher becomes a decisive agent in the student's life, with a role of great importance. According to De Moraes, Da Silva and Cunha (2004, p. 16), "education and training are considered specific and goal-oriented forms of instruction, providing professionals with knowledge and skills so that they can play their roles".

The teaching and learning process must be seen as a series of steps and participants, including the teacher. The teacher is the figure responsible for being the mediator of the knowledge and knowledge obtained by the student. The school must be the environment for interaction between students and teachers. Neves and Damiani (2006, p. 9) demonstrate this

when they exemplify the ideas of “Vygotsky, who rescues the importance of the school and the role of the teacher as indispensable agents of the teaching-learning process”.

Peres et al. (2014) and Giusta (1985) also report the student's relationship with obtaining their knowledge in school subjects. In this sense, knowledge must occur in concrete situations, related to the socio-historical content and grounded in a transforming pedagogy of society, such as the Progressive Pedagogy of Libâneo, the Problematization of Bordenave, the Critical-Reproductivists of Saviani and the Cognitivist of Mizukami .

This relationship should be seen as alternatives for the development of contextualized, dynamic classes with updated content according to reality. It is also up to the teacher to become aware of the profile of each student in the face of learning theories and make use of technological tools, activities that seek activities in groups, which provide collective and collaborative knowledge.

The teacher must seek knowledge and training to make use of learning theories. An essential task is for teachers to know how to use these theories and apply them in their classes. Furthermore, this teacher must be a mediating and transforming agent of the student's reality.

It becomes necessary for teachers to redo the planning, so that they are able to develop activities consistent with these students and that seek the evolution of knowledge and knowledge. It is also essential to use learning theories as an educational and pedagogical tool, as well as applying them in the classroom.

Conclusion

Learning theories represent important pillars and instruments to be used in the classroom. The teacher is aware of the existence of these theories linked to Educational Psychology, but they do not use them or still do not know how to use them.

In a classroom it is possible to find different styles of students, with their particular learning characteristics, successes and failures. Learning theories make it possible to plan and design classes according to the representatives and thinkers of each school and theory.

Therefore, external factors, such as poor school performance, sociocultural and family influences, among others, can be analyzed in light of the various existing theories.

It is necessary for educators to develop the ability to think, to awaken the critical sense and ensure the effective learning of students. It is also extremely important to use and apply learning theories in the educational and pedagogical scope.

Teachers should seek knowledge of these theories, as well as the best ways to apply them.

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